

Exploring the Perspectives and Opportunities of Employment of Transgender in Gujarat, India

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Abstract

Indian constitution unequivocally states that in Article 14 no state shall deny equality before the law and equal protection to its people within the Union of India, Article 19(a) protects the right to freedom of speech and expression, and Article 21 guarantees the Protection of life and personal liberty which by extension gives the right to live with dignity. But in several cases, these essential key rights are denied to certain individuals as a result of their sexual orientation. There are at least 4.8 lakh transgenders in India and the social acknowledgment of transgender individuals in India is not equivalent to that of a male or female sex. The paper explores various challenges faced by transgender individuals at workplace and in their career. A qualitative study was conducted on 130 transgender through snowball sampling. The responses were video recorded for further behavioral analysis. Behavioral and emotional aspects of transgender were explored with respect to their acceptance in the corporate world. The paper concludes with stress on the requirement of sensitization and gaps in the society in creating a holistic ecosystem of survival of all genders in professional world.

Keywords: Transgender, third gender, legal, sex identity, LGBTQ, homosexual, fundamental rights, sexual orientation, judgement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid changes in workforce composition around the world have forced establishments to embrace and appreciate diversity of the workforce in terms of culture, traditions, sexual orientation etc. Inclusiveness in workforce is essential for organisations to retain their competitive edge and stay an attractive workplace to varying population. Workplace diversity means “acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing, and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual practice, and public assistance status.” Green et al. (2002). It is not just enough to employ people from diverse backgrounds but embrace and celebrate their diversity at workplace (Green et al., 2002).

Today establishments have improved to the extent of including and promoting women and people with disabilities as employees but transgenders have seldom benefitted from this exercise. Employers shy away from employing transgender individuals to evade the burden of designing and monitoring new human resource (HR) policies, change the physical infrastructure, introduce new training modules, orient existing employees to work with transgender co-workers etc. This has rendered transgender individuals devoid of their fundamental right to work recognized by the world community and the same issue has also been neglected by the body of researchers (Chakrapani et al., 2015)

Transgender individuals experience the highest degree of discrimination in employment and at workplace, as stated by a study on sexual orientation and gender identity discrimination at work by International Labour Organisation (ILO, 2013). Human Resource Management (HRM) should start moving away from their conventional way of operating and find ways to include the sexual minority as they have now become a significant part of the global talent pool (McPhail et al., 2014; Day & Greene, 2008). They need to be better prepared to address difficulties and an ever increasingly diverse workforce (Gedro et al., 2013; McPhail et al., 2014). Slowly efforts are being made to bring workplaces issues of the lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer (LGBTQ) from the periphery to the centre (Bell et al., 2011; Wilkinson et al., 2014), still there are miles to go before their voices are heard and issues resolved.

There is still a substantial gap in the theoretical and empirical literatures on specific challenges transgender individuals are subjected to at the workplace and their possible solutions, since these issues have majorly been understudied in HRM and diversity management research (Law et al.,

2011). Further, research on employees who are sexual minorities is often focused on everyone in the LGBTQ community except transgenders, when they may not have the same workplace problems (Richardson & Monro, 2012).

This study finds its aim in the commitment to remedy this neglect. The research questions we pose are categorised into their communication skills, emotional maturity to handle daily situations, confidence in their physical appearance, professional ethics self-empowerment and their social comfort. The questions are further designed in understanding the dynamics of their experience with each category definition. Each question is designed into five likert scale from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. The statements are like “When I talk to someone, I worry about what other people think about me”, “I understand that my fears are unreasonable but I feel I am helpless to control them”, “The choice of my dressing is dictated by society”, “I think it is important to have new experiences that challenges how you think about yourself and others”, “I want to achieve higher education because it will solve my future problems”, “Fear of embarrassment or humiliation, keeps me away from doing things that I really want to do.” There are multiple social stigma and stereotype mind-set of the society which curbs the potential of the community and are creating constraints for their social acceptance. The main objective of the entire research is to nullify the stigma and give them the leverage to live their life as the normal citizen as it has been legalised and approved at multiple platforms. The final contribution of the paper is practised oriented.

On a parallel front the research paper also creates a window of opportunities at the corporate employment level, wherein the recruitment gates are opened without any biasness and stereotyping involved. The community should be analysed on the basis of their skill, attitude and knowledge and not their hormonal and sexual orientation status. The right for education and expression also is highlighted in the below research which is a much-needed requirement at corporate, society and research level.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Despite profiting from a feeling of minority solidarity, transgender individuals experience marginalisation and disempowerment among the LGBTQ community (Browne & Lim, 2010). Thus, the diversity management frameworks must combine gender identity diversity with other important aspects rather than keeping in at the periphery.

2.1 Evolution of Diversity Management

The concept of managing diversity at workplace originated from the US in the mid-1980s as an HR initiative. Owing to many social movements, large scale political and regulatory changes, it was majorly focused on gender and race diversity (due to infusion of immigrants) (e.g. Heilman, 1997; Nkomo, 1992). This became a technique to retain employees and promote career development (Agocs & Burr, 1996). Eventually other parameters like age, disability, religion and culture, social class and sexual orientation were covered under diversity management (Clair Creed et al., 2005; Creed et al., 2010; Ghumman & Ryan, 2013), but general spotlight sustained to be on gender and race diversity. Therefore, LGBT concerns, especially of transgender individuals are largely neglected in the wider diversity management field (Bowen & Blackmon, 2003; Ozturk & Rumens, 2014).

The Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), a British association for academics and HR professionals and, has defined diversity reasonably as “valuing everyone as an individual” (CIPD, 2006). It has also given three reasons to enhance diversity management: efficient people management, market competition and corporate reputation. Providing an inclusive workplace culture wherein all feel welcomed and cherished helps to select and retain talents. A diverse workforce can naturally result in improved market share and broadening of an organization's customer base and showcase their dedication to corporate social responsibility (CSR) through engagement with local communities (CIPD, 2006).

However, this normative view of treasuring diversity as endorsed in the USA has not necessarily translated similarly in the Indian context. Many of the parameters of diversity management in the West are accepted by the society and protected by law. In India, the main sources of diversity are caste, religion and gender (Kundu, 2003; Ratnam & Chandra, 1996). And eradication of social inequality is planned to be achieved through a top-down approach by introducing government policies and regulations (Cooke, 2011). In India, diversity management is mostly restricted to encouraging female empowerment and employing the disabled (Cooke & Saini, 2012).

One of the most prominent political conflicts Indians have witnessed, lies in the legal discrimination for the LGBTQ community (Sharma S, 2021) which undermines and prejudices fundamental human rights for certain civilians of our country. The question lies in whether this major discrepancy between homosexual and heterosexual intimacies (Falbo & Peplau, 1980) have

rational grounds to it or not. The basic idea of human right is that every individual is ought to be treated equally and with respect and the infringement of such rights results in discrimination (Beer & Mitchell, 2006).). Human Rights are natural rights; they are unavoidable, indestructible rights that are presented to man since their birth.

2.2 Indian Scenario

Indian culture could be considered as one of the most divergent, vivid, rich, and dynamic societies with scientific temper. The nearness of homosexuality in Indian history is very much saved in relics from ancient times that were reported in the old writings like Kama sutra and Manuscripts. The old Indian cultural perspectives about homosexuality were not inflexible but rather adaptable and logical. The establishment work of Hindu law, the Manu Smriti (200 BC-200 AD) clarifies the biological origin of the three genders (Sharma, A. (2018)). History specialists have since a long time ago contended that pre-colonial Indian culture did not criticize same-sex intimate relations, nor did it view such relations as shameless or wicked. Hinduism, India's biggest religion, has generally projected homosexuality as common and cheerful. Today the transgender individuals are known as Hijras, Eunuchs, Kothis, Aravanis, Jogappas, Shiv-Shakthis etc., who have been a part of the Indian society for centuries.

In mainstream society transvestism is a marker of embarrassment. The most ideal approach to embarrass a man is to make him wear female clothing. "Wear bangles and sit home" is a typical expression to affront a man. Be that as it may, Lord Krishna transforms the affront into acclaim. Krishna tales are brimming with references of cross-dressing. The account of Krishna wearing Radha's garments and Radha wearing Krishna's garments is frequently called the story of the 'white cowherd'.

Hijras assumed a renowned job in the regal courts of the Islamic world, especially in the Ottoman realms and the Mughal rule in Medieval India. They achieved notable positions as political counsels, administrators, generals just as gatekeepers of the harems. Hijras were known to be smart, dependable and wildly faithful and had free access to all spaces and areas of populace. The Hijras likewise involved high posts in the Islamic religious organizations, particularly in

safeguarding the holy places of Mecca and Medina, they had the option to impact state choices and furthermore got enormous measure of cash to have been nearest to kings and queens.

In later half of the nineteenth century, the colonial organization enthusiastically looked to condemn the hijra community and deprive them of the common rights. They were viewed as a different caste or clan in various pieces of India by the frontier organization. The Criminal Tribes Act, 1871, incorporated all hijras who were concerned with hijacking and mutilating kids and dressed like ladies to move out in the public spots. The discipline for such exercises was as long as two years detainment and a fine or on the other hand both. This pre-partition history impacts the helpless conditions of hijras currently (Michelraj, 2015).

Indian census has never seen the third sexual orientation, i.e., transgender while accumulating data for a long period of time. Be that as it may, in the Census of 2011, data of transgender individuals were gathered in the class of "Others" under Gender with details identified with their business, education, and caste. This census declared the population of these individuals to be around 4.88 lakh. The information has been basically associated with the male section as they are normally considered men, yet on demand, they might be viewed as women. Along these lines, it is difficult to remark on the genuine transgender population. The 2011 evaluation additionally revealed 55,000 youngsters as transgenders identified by their parents. (Sawant N, 2017)

There are at least 4.8 lakh transgenders in India and the social acknowledgment of transgender individuals in India is not equivalent to that of a male or female sex. A study done in Bangalore indicated that 45% of the transgender members saw that they have a good quality life (QOL) and 13.3% of the members reacted that they have an excellent QOL. By and large a moderate to great degree of QOL of the transgenders were found in adults. The relationship between overall QOL and monthly income was found to be measurably significant (Naskar et al., 2018). The primary issue with some orthodox individuals is the absence of appropriate mindfulness and in particular no comprehension with the transgender network and furthermore that such a large number of individuals don't acknowledge transgender as a person. Be that as it may, as the time changes, the individuals of the general public are changing now. Society has begun to recognize their conditions and what they all face in their daily routine (Agarwal, 2019).

2.3 Trials at Workplace for Transgender Employees

There is lack of conducive environment for education of transgender individuals in India and organizations often complain about lack of qualified people among this community. Most of them are school drop-outs or lack skillset needed to get a job. Therefore, most of the challenges in the path of career for these individuals start the stage of recruitment. Further employers shy away from employing transgender individuals in areas like canteen, housekeeping etc. where no special skills are needed. This shows the employers are deliberately dodging the hassles that come from employing anyone from the LGBTQ community (Philip & Soumyaja, 2019).

Exclusion, underestimation and stigmatisation often colour experiences of transgender individuals at their workplace. They tend to self-strategise to endure threats of disclosure of their sexual identity at their workplace, resulting in added stress. Disclosure disconnects generate unique diversity management challenges centred on employee well-being, as they often entail ‘psychological stress, role conflict, attributional ambiguity, and a pressure to establish congruent identities across life domains’ (Ragins, 2008).

Another significant area in the context of transgender workplace issues is ‘transitioning’. Transgender individuals may resist getting categorized into traditional gender categories and this may create confusion and anxiety in the establishment (Roen, 2002).

There is structural exclusion practiced in India wherein people from the transgender community are not even called for an interview. Further, problems not just end by merely employing transgender individuals, they also find difficulties in obtaining accommodation, unable to emotionally connect with colleagues, feeling discriminated at work etc. All these problems stem from one notion that these individuals are not accepted and understood by the society easily (Philip & Soumyaja, 2019).

2.4 Legal Aspects

Homosexual people are dealt with unreasonably on the basis of their individual choices, sexual inclinations and their orientation, in this way that restrains them to live with pride and respect (Article 21). They are compelled to shroud their character and are not given any reinforcement and positive surroundings that can help them in understanding their maximum capacity.

2.4.1 Section 377

“Whoever voluntarily has carnal intercourse against the order of nature with any man, woman or animal shall be punished with imprisonment for life, or with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to ten years, and shall also be liable to fine.”

Explanation- Penetration is sufficient to constitute the carnal intercourse necessary to the offence described in this section."

While discussing queer issues in India, Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code has risen as a critical highlight to discuss about. Similarly, as with all communities that are mistreated in the public arena and as we see, it isn't just the law that adds to their unprivileged status in the public eye. There are various different factors, for example, social taboo, thoughts of custom, culture, etc. Law is one part of this aggregation of instruments that are utilized to abuse a range of various individuals. No mistreated communities throughout the entire existence of mankind has been a special case to this standard. (Agarwal, A. (2019).)

As indicated by this law, any sort of sexual activity that is not penovaginal ('intercourse' as utilized in the clarification typically implies penile-vaginal intercourse in Indian law) is culpable. This law then condemns sexual action between two consenting grown-ups. This law was established in 1860 in British India, simultaneously as in England itself, is normal to numerous former colonies of Britain and in this manner is normal to most nations in South Asia.

This arrangement has been used generally against gay men, hijras and male sex workers in general society circle. It has likewise been used against organizations and activists at the grassroots level taking a shot at issues of sexual rights, LGBT issues and HIV/AIDS. It is important to take notice that from 1860 there have been not many instances of arrest and prosecution under Sec.377. The section be that as it may, we know from testimonial proof, has been utilized for provocation of gay, MSM and hijras in the open circle by police authorities and in the private by families and companions. (Arasu. P., Thangarajah)

2.4.2 The Historic Verdict of Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India

On 27 April 2016, five individuals filed a new writ petition in the Supreme Court testing the lawfulness of Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code. The petitioners asserted that the issues which they brought forth in their petition were different from those raised in the pending curative petition in the 2013 Koushal v. Naz case, in which the Supreme Court had upheld the legitimacy of Section 377.

On 6 September 2018, the court ruled that LGBT people in India are entitled to all constitutional rights, including the liberties protected by the Constitution of India. The judgment also made note that LGBT community is entitled to equal citizenship and protection under law, without discrimination. (Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India.) The judgment strengthens four fundamental ideas: dignity, privacy, equity and non-discrimination, for transgender individuals.

3. DATA ANALYSIS APPROACH

The research was done with snowball sampling. There was an in-depth literature review done to understand the key parameters and frame them in the questionnaire. The unstructured questionnaire was even later on customised in the basis of population sensitivity. The respondents were mostly illiterate or were not well versed with English so the surveyor would attempt in verbal explanation of questions and collect the responses accordingly. During the transaction even video recording was done to collect more content through their body language and facial expression. Various NGOs like Lakshya Trust, Vadodara also supported for identifying the population. The responses were captured in quantitative format and related analysis were done accordingly.

Fig 1: Research Methodology

3.1 Participation Profile

A total of 130 transgender participated across Gujarat where in majority of them were associated with Lakshya Trust. The respondents are categorised according to their age, employment status, family setup and education qualification.

Fig 2: Respondent's age profile

Note: The respondent's age were from the range of 19 to 50 where in majority of the population were inclined towards 19-30 age.

Fig 3: Respondent's employment profile

Majority of the respondents (64%) were employed under the profession like chef, beautician etc. 29% of the respondents were unemployed. There was also presence of some sex workers (3%).

Fig 4: Respondent family set up

78% of the respondents were from nuclear family setup and remaining were from the joint family set up. In spite of the family's presence majority of them were out casted from the society and were forced to take shelter in the community or NGOs like Lakshya Trust to maintain their security and well-being.

Fig 5: Respondent's Education Profile

Majority of them were education with minimum degree of 10th pass. There was a presence of some master degree holder as well.

4. KEY FINDINGS

The inferences of the data were done on the basis of the analysis of 38 statements. All the statements were categorised into six categories: Communication skills, Emotional Maturity, Physical Appearance, Professional Commitment, Self-Empowerment and Social Acceptance.

The demographics of the population is collected on the basis of age, employment status, education, family set up and family income.

4.1 An Overview of feedback on Physical appearance

The comfort of the respondents on the basis of their physical appearance are analysed on the basis of the following statements.

Ques 10 *The choice of my dressing is dictated by society.*

Ques 27 *I am always careful about my manner of dressing.*

Ques 11 *It is my choice and decision to wear what I want to wear every day.*

Ques 12 *I regularly abuse alcohol or illicit substances such as marijuana, cocaine, etc. as a part of my grooming.*

The below mentioned table suggests the Positive and Negative feedback on their physical appearance

	Ques 10	Ques 27	Ques 11	Ques 12
<2.5 (Positive)	27%	65%	85%	92%
>=2.5 (Negative)	73%	35%	15%	8%

Table 1: The Positive and Negative feedback on their physical appearance

The below mentioned are the highlights of the feedback received.

Fig 6: Highlights of feedback on their physical appearance

4.2 An Overview of feedback on Communication

The communication with the respondents was analysed by understanding the response on the below mentioned six statements

Ques 14 *I hesitate to interact with people outside my community*

Ques 18 *I usually get into arguments to prove my point*

Ques 19 *I find it difficult to talk to effectively*

Ques 20 *I can express my views appropriately to others*

Ques 21 *I am unable to speak-up in front of a gathering*

Ques 24 *When I talk to someone, I worry about what other people think about me*

The below mentioned table suggests the Positive and Negative feedback on their communication skills.

	Ques 14	Ques 18	Ques 19	Ques 20	Ques 21	Ques 24
<2.5 (Positive)	65%	77%	62%	96%	65%	58%
>=2.5 (Negative)	35%	23%	38%	4%	35%	42%

Table 2: The Positive and Negative feedback on their communication skills

Fig 7: Highlights of feedback on their communication skills

4.3 An Overview of feedback on Emotional Maturity

The emotional maturity of the respondents are analysed on the basis nine statements.

Ques 6. *I feel positive and creative about myself*

Ques 8. *I feel eager to tackle my daily task or make new decisions*

Ques 15. *I feel embarrassed and scared in a group of new people*

Ques 16. *It is easy for me to mix with other people*

Ques 23. *If I get to know people are forming a negative impression of me, it disturbs me*

Ques 25. *If I know that someone is judging me, it affects me*

Ques 28. *I understand that my fears are unreasonable but I feel I am helpless to control them*

Ques 35. *Morality is required to function properly*

Ques 37. *I wish that I face problems bravely*

The below mentioned table suggests the Positive and Negative feedback on their emotional maturity.

	Ques 6	Ques 8	Ques 15	Ques 16	Ques 23	Ques 25	Ques 28	Ques 35	Ques 37
<2.5 (Positive)	77%	81%	31%	73%	35%	38%	42%	85%	4%
>=2.5 (Negative)	23%	19%	69%	27%	65%	62%	58%	15%	96%

Table3: The Positive and Negative feedback on their emotional maturity

Fig 8: Highlights of feedback on their emotional maturity

4.4 An Overview of feedback on Self-Empowerment

The self-empowerment of the candidates is analysed on the basis of the following six statements

- Ques 5. In my daily life I get a chance to show how capable I am*
- Ques 31. I want to achieve higher education because of my parents*
- Ques 32. I want to achieve higher education because it will solve my future problems*
- Ques 33. I want to achieve higher education because I want to help others*
- Ques 34. Money is the most important thing in life*
- Ques 36. It is important to be self-dependent*

	Ques 5	Ques 31	Ques 32	Ques 33	Ques 34	Ques 36
<2.5 (Positive)	85%	65%	65%	50%	58%	85%
>=2.5 (Negative)	15%	35%	35%	50%	42%	15%

Table 4: The Positive and Negative feedback on their self-empowerment

Fig 9: Highlights of feedback on their self-empowerment

4.5 An Overview of feedback on Social Comfort

The social comfort of the respondents was analysed on the basis of six statements

Ques 13. *I don't bother what people think about me*

Ques 17. *I don't think others are able to understand me*

Ques 26. *I avoid social situations in which I might meet new people because of extreme discomfort*

Ques 29. *Fear of embarrassment or humiliation, keeps me away from doing things that I really want to do.*

Ques 30. *I usually avoid use of public facilities*

Ques 38. *I wish be an integral part of my family again*

	Ques 13	Ques 17	Ques 26	Ques 29	Ques 30	Ques 38
<2.5 (Positive)	46%	54%	46%	46%	46%	15%
>=2.5 (Negative)	54%	46%	54%	54%	54%	85%

Table 5: The Positive and Negative feedback on their social comfort

Fig 10: Highlights of feedback on their social comfort

4.6 An Overview of feedback on Professional Ethics

The professional ethics of the respondents are analysed on the basis of the following seven statements

Ques 1. *Management here does everything it can to provide the employees an accommodating infrastructure and environment*

Ques 2. *Management ignores our suggestions and complaints*

Ques 3. *My supervisor/boss has always been fair in their dealing with me*

Ques 4. *The people I work with behave in a friendly manner*

Ques 7. *I feel like I am capable of working hard*

Ques 9. *I think it is important to have new experiences that challenges how you think about yourself and others*

Ques 22. *I have difficulty in making my voice heard*

	Ques 1	Ques 2	Ques 3	Ques 4	Ques 7	Ques 9	Ques 22
<2.5 (Positive)	62%	31%	65%	69%	92%	85%	42%
>=2.5 (Negative)	38%	69%	35%	31%	8%	15%	58%

Table 6: The Positive and Negative feedback on their professional ethics

Fig 11: Highlights of feedback on their professional ethics

5. CONCLUSION

Transgender individuals experience obstacles to their careers, which begin right at the stage of recruitment and selections stage and endure them throughout their working lives. Without solid enforcement of equality law that handle these hindrances particularly experienced by gender identity minorities, they convey absence of trust and confidence in progress towards better depiction. In that situation, for many of our respondents, the hope lies in external pressure put on companies in order to push establishments to increase transgender representation. Transgender employees in industries that are particularly unwelcoming to gender identity diversity find it necessary to opt for a change in career, making compromises in pay and rewards, and surrendering hard-earned privilege and position as they go into last-resort jobs.

Seldom does our overall population recognizes or cares to comprehend the misery, anguish and torment which the transgender individuals experience, nor recognizes the inborn sentiments of the transgender individuals, particularly of those whose brain and body reject their natural sex. Our society regularly mocks and abuses the transgender individuals in open spots like railroad stations, transport stands, schools, work environments, shopping centers, theaters, emergency clinics, they are neglected and treated as untouchables, overlooking the way that the moral disappointment lies in the general public's reluctance to contain or embrace diverse sexual identities and articulations, an outlook which we need to change. Most transgender individuals, mostly youth, face innumerable difficulties in managing one's own sexual orientation which inverse to that of the gender identity and gender role forced on them based on their natural gender. They face a few issues, for example, disgrace, dread, and disguised trans-fear; and coming out; changing, adjusting, or not adjusting to social pressure; dread of connections or loss of connections; and purposeful restrictions on demeanor or goals. Transgenders are also a part of the community and they have equivalent right to everything on the planet that is available to each and every person.

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